

Exact Spin Elimination in Ising Hamiltonians and Energy-Based Machine Learning

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Abstract

We present an exact spin-elimination technique that reduces the dimensionality of both quadratic and k -local Ising Hamiltonians while preserving their original ground-state configurations. By systematically replacing each removed spin with an effective interaction among its neighbors, our method lowers the total spin count without invoking approximations or iterative recalculations. This capability is especially beneficial for hardware-constrained platforms, classical or quantum, that can directly implement multi-body interactions but have limited qubit or spin resources. We demonstrate three key advances enabled by this technique. First, we handle larger instances of benchmark problems such as Max-Cut on cubic graphs without exceeding a 2-local interaction limit. Second, we reduce qubit requirements in QAOA-based integer factorization on near-term quantum devices, thus extending the feasible range of integers to be factorized. Third, we improve memory capacity in Hopfield associative memories and enhance memory retrieval by suppressing spurious attractors, enhancing retrieval performance. Our spin-elimination procedure trades local spin complexity for higher-order couplings or higher node degrees in a single pass, opening new avenues for scaling up combinatorial optimization and energy-based machine learning on near-term hardware. Finally, these results underscore that the next-generation physical spin machines will likely capitalize on k -local spin Hamiltonians to offer an alternative to classical computations.

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1 Introduction

Combinatorial optimization underpins a vast array of scientific and industrial applications, including logistics [1], economic and finance [2], materials discovery [3], quantum field theory [4] and quantum gravity [5], as well as artificial intelligence and machine learning applications [6]. A common strategy for formulating such problems is to map them onto an Ising Hamiltonian, in which each binary decision variable is represented by a spin $s_i \in \{\pm 1\}$. For an N -spin system, the conventional (2-local) Ising Hamiltonian can be expressed as

$$H(s_1, \dots, s_N) = \sum_{i=1, j < i}^N J_{ij} s_i s_j + \sum_{i=1}^N \chi_i s_i, \quad (1)$$

where J_{ij} describes pairwise interactions between spins s_i and s_j , and χ_i is an external bias on spin s_i . Finding the Hamiltonian's ground state then corresponds to identifying the global optimum of the original combinatorial problem.

Because of this direct link between Ising Hamiltonians and combinatorial optimization (and noting that such ground-state determination is generally NP-hard [7]), a range of hardware platforms has emerged to solve Ising-like models by seeking low-energy configurations. These include quantum annealers, such as D-Wave Systems’ devices [8], which implement adiabatic protocols to reach low-energy Ising configurations; gate-based quantum processors that implement Variational Quantum Algorithms (VQAs), notably the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) [9]; physics-inspired hardware, including Fujitsu’s Digital Annealer (FDA) [10], Toshiba’s Simulated Bifurcation Machine (SBM) [11], and Microsoft’s Analog Iterative Machine (AIM) [12], that mimic relaxation dynamics to locate minima; Ising Machines such as Coherent Ising Machines (CIMs), based on optical parametric oscillators [13, 14], spatial-light-modulator (SLM) systems such as Spatial Photonic Ising Machine (SPIM)[15, 16, 17, 18], surface amplitude wave Ising machines [19], spinwave Ising Machines [20], Ising Machines based on subharmonic electrical resonators [21], Probabilistic Ising Machines [22, 23], Chaotic Ising Machines [24] and many others [25, 26].

Some of these architectures mandate an embedding step to map a fully connected Ising problem onto hardware-limited connectivity (e.g., a sparse qubit graph). Such embeddings can drastically inflate the number of spins from N to $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$, leading to dimensionality blow-up and associated scalability constraints [27]. In contrast, platforms with nearly all-to-all connectivity (e.g., CIMs, SPIMs, FDA, SBM, AIM) mitigate these overheads by sidestepping the need for chain-like embeddings.

Many real-world problems entail interactions beyond simple pairwise terms, naturally resulting in *higher-order* Ising Hamiltonians (or Polynomial Unconstrained Binary Optimization [28, 29]). While mainstream quantum algorithms (e.g., quantum annealing and QAOA) are designed for quadratic (2-local) Hamiltonians, one can encode higher-order interactions by introducing auxiliary spins to rewrite each multi-body term as a collection of pairwise couplings [30]. However, this so-called *quadratization* increases the problem’s dimensionality and may compromise the potential scalability benefits of the hardware. In contrast, certain machines, including advanced coherent-optical or analog platforms, can handle higher-order (k -body) terms directly, avoiding the auxiliary-spin overhead [31]. Memristor-based hardware [32, 33], superconducting devices [34, 35], trapped ions [36, 37] all demonstrated k -local Ising minimization. Regardless of whether an Ising Hamiltonian is 2-local or k -local, the number of spins is a critical bottleneck for physical optimizers. Reducing the dimensionality of the Ising formulation can 1) simplify problem structure for classical or quantum optimization routines, 2) enable larger-scale problem instances on hardware with strict qubit or spin limits, and 3) lower overhead.

This importance explains why reducing the number of spin variables in an Ising Hamiltonian while preserving its ground state has been an active research topic in optimization theory, physics, and machine learning. Spin elimination encompasses techniques that fix or remove selected variables based on analytical criteria, producing a smaller equivalent problem whose ground state matches the original’s. Such methods include pseudo-Boolean optimization strategies [38], recursive variable-elimination algorithms [39], renormalization-inspired approaches [40], and quantum-based techniques such as spin fixing [41].

The roof duality relaxation in pseudo-Boolean optimization computes a bound on the minimum energy and identifies any spins whose orientations are the same in all optimal solutions [38]. These persistently oriented spins can be fixed without compromising global optimality, effectively reducing the problem size. Reintroducing the fixed spins after solving the smaller Ising model recovers the original ground state. This preprocessing step has been incorporated into both classical combinatorial solvers and quantum annealing workflows; for instance, D-Wave’s

software applies roof duality to precompute persistencies before annealing [42].

A related basic algorithm recursively eliminates variables by assigning each binary variable to its locally optimal value, given the other variables [38]. Eliminating one variable at a time and updating the Hamiltonian reduces the system dimension at each step. Under suitable conditions (e.g., unimodality of the energy in each variable), this process guarantees a global optimum. The procedure parallels Gaussian elimination in linear systems and is closely associated with the persistency concept. Analogous principles appear in constraint propagation for SAT solvers and in cutting-plane methods for 0–1 programming [43, 44]. Although SAT solvers do not minimize an energy function, they often fix variables when a clause becomes a unit (all but one literal is false), effectively removing the free choice for that variable. The Davis–Putnam procedure illustrates such variable elimination, resolving clauses to produce an equivalent formula without the chosen variable [45]. A similar viewpoint applies in 0–1 integer programming [43, 44], where eliminating a variable projects the feasible set onto a lower-dimensional space and often introduces new valid inequalities. Branch-and-reduce approaches likewise rely on partial variable elimination at each node to simplify subproblems [39].

A further class of spin-elimination methods emerges in physics through renormalization group (RG) techniques [40]. RG commonly integrates out or decimates spins to yield an effective Hamiltonian with fewer degrees of freedom, striving to preserve ground-state properties. Strong-disorder RG, for example, iteratively eliminates the spin subject to the largest field or coupling and introduces a new effective interaction among that spin’s neighbors [40]. If a spin with local field χ_i is removed, any spins j, k coupled to i acquire a direct coupling $J'_{jk} \approx J_{ji}J_{ik}/\chi_i$. Alternatively, if the strongest term is a bond J_{ij} , the spins i and j may be merged into one cluster with an effective field. Although RG methods are generally approximate, they can preserve the ground state under certain conditions (e.g., in one-dimensional or hierarchical models). Graph-based reductions similarly merge strongly ferromagnetically coupled spins into a single effective spin or remove redundant spins introduced by constraints [46].

Spin fixing also appears in hybrid quantum-classical algorithms designed to operate under limited qubit resources [41]. By solving part of the problem classically (or using a heuristic) and fixing those spin values, the residual subproblem (now smaller) can be transferred to a quantum device. Recursive QAOA (RQAOA) further demonstrates how iterative correlation measurements can drive spin fixing and thus reduce problem size. However, repeated approximations may introduce noise and computational overhead, risking minor degradation of solution fidelity [47]. The recently proposed Quantum-Informed Recursive Optimization (QIRO) framework pushes this idea further by feeding QAOA-derived correlations into problem-specific classical reductions and backtracking loops [48]. While QIRO can outperform classical heuristics, it still relies on iterative calls to quantum hardware (or simulators) and on correlation-rounding approximations. Our method achieves an equivalent variable reduction in a single classical pass, making it immediately deployable on both purely classical and quantum-native k -local hardware without additional quantum measurements. Sample-persistence variable-reduction (SPVAR) heuristics fix spins that take identical values across a pool of low-energy samples, shrinking the problem before re-annealing [49]. Because SPVAR decisions are probabilistic and can be wrong, multiple restarts (or elite-set filtering) are needed. Our elimination gadgets are deterministic and provably preserve the exact ground state, so no restarts or statistical thresholds are required.

However, each of these spin-elimination and variable-fixing strategies can become computationally demanding in large systems, given the combinatorial explosion in possible variable assignments. Thus, a key research goal is to design elimination methods that are both efficient

and exact for real-world problem sizes while being adaptable to a broad class of interaction graphs.

In contrast, we propose a novel and exact spin-elimination procedure that operates directly on 2-local or k -local Ising Hamiltonians using universal (general-form) elimination gadgets. Although this approach is most effective for certain graph topologies and degree distributions that match these gadgets, the application itself scales polynomially in the system size. The procedure systematically removes spins while ensuring that the ground state of the reduced Hamiltonian remains identical to that of the original system. Rather than resorting to iterative, recursive procedures, which can lead to increasingly complicated interactions and become computationally overwhelming for large systems, we propose direct elimination gadgets that immediately substitute an eliminated spin’s contributions with interactions among its neighbors. This preserves the original ground-state configuration while reducing the dimensionality of the system.

The exact nature of our method guarantees that no approximation is introduced during spin elimination, thereby allowing a straightforward back-mapping from the reduced Hamiltonian to the original variables. Moreover, by leveraging hardware platforms capable of implementing multi-body couplings directly, our approach avoids the dimensionality blow-up commonly associated with quadratization [30]. As a result, we enable systematic spin-count reduction while retaining critical ground-state properties, which is particularly beneficial for devices with limited qubit or spin resources.

There are other methods that should be mentioned. For instance, a recent spin-variable-reduction (SVR) method rewrites linear equality constraints by expressing dependent spins as analytic functions of a reduced independent set, thereby lowering the total spin count without penalties [50]. Unlike SVR, which is tailored to equality constraints and still ends up with a quadratic Hamiltonian, our gadgets remove any spin (constrained or not) in one step while preserving higher-order couplings exactly, so the ground state remains unchanged even for non-linear or unconstrained instances.

In what follows, we formalize the spin-elimination method, introduce several gadgets, and demonstrate how they can be applied to large-scale problems. We also illustrate the broader concept that increasing interaction order while decreasing spin count can offer practical benefits to hardware architectures that support multi-body interactions but are constrained by limited physical resources. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we develop the theoretical groundwork for our approach to single-step spin elimination and introduce the necessary gadget constructions. We then apply our method to several benchmark problems in Sections 3 and 4, including the 3-regular Max-Cut problem and the J-Möbius Ladder. There, we show that our technique can handle Max-Cut instances up to 50% larger without increasing coupling locality. In Section 5, we turn to machine learning applications, demonstrating a significant boost in the memory capacity of Hopfield networks. In Section 6, we address integer factorization, illustrating how our approach enables record-size numbers to be factorized on near-term devices. In these examples, single-step spin elimination reduces the number of spins while preserving the original ground state, leading to more efficient optimization on both quantum and classical solvers. We conclude in Section 7.

2 K-Local Ising Hamiltonian

Let $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_N)$ be a configuration of N Ising spins with each $s_i \in \{\pm 1\}$. We consider a general k -local Ising-type Hamiltonian (also historically called the p -order Ising spin glass

[51]) of the form

$$H(s_1, \dots, s_N) = \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{1, \dots, N\} \\ |\mathcal{S}| \leq k}} c_{\mathcal{S}} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i, \quad (2)$$

where each subset $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{1, \dots, N\}$ of cardinality up to k has an associated real coupling coefficient $c_{\mathcal{S}}$. Equivalently, one may label these subsets by $m = 1, \dots, M$ to write

$$H(\mathbf{s}) = \sum_{m=1}^M c_m \Phi_m(\mathbf{s}), \quad \text{where } \Phi_m(\mathbf{s}) = \prod_{j \in \mathcal{S}_m} s_j \quad \text{and} \quad c_m \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (3)$$

The term $\Phi_m(\mathbf{s})$ is thus a product of at most k spins, and the problem of minimizing $H(\mathbf{s})$ is, in general, NP-hard [28]. Nonetheless, specialized hardware or solvers may tackle certain k -local forms more efficiently than large-scale embeddings of 2-local Hamiltonians [29, 31, 52].

A central tool in our approach is *spin elimination*, in which a chosen spin s_a is removed from the system by absorbing its local contributions into an effective, possibly higher-order term among its neighbors. Let \mathbf{s}_{nbr} be the set of spins that appear jointly with s_a in any of the Hamiltonian terms. Collect all terms in $H(\mathbf{s})$ that involve s_a into a *local block*:

$$H_{\text{local}}(s_a; \mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} c_m (s_a \Psi_m(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})) \equiv s_a P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}), \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{M} indexes these terms, $\Psi_m(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}) = \prod_{\ell \in \mathcal{S}_m \setminus \{a\}} s_{\ell}$ is the product of the neighbor spins in the m -th term, c_m is the corresponding coupling coefficient, and $P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})$ is a multilinear polynomial in the neighbor spins only.

To eliminate s_a , observe that for any fixed configuration \mathbf{s}_{nbr} , the contribution $s_a P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})$ is linear in $s_a \in \{\pm 1\}$. Its minimum is $-|P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})|$, implying that we can replace $s_a P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})$ in the Hamiltonian H with $-|P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})|$ and further with a $F(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})$, a multilinear polynomial in \mathbf{s}_{nbr} matching $-|P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})|$ on all spin configurations. This replacement captures the fact that s_a will adopt whichever sign minimizes that local energy. The quantity $F(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}) = -|P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}})|$ is then recast as a sum of monomials solely in \mathbf{s}_{nbr} . In general, this can elevate the interaction order among \mathbf{s}_{nbr} , yet it reduces the total dimension N of the system by removing s_a . Once the remaining spins \mathbf{s}_{nbr} are optimized, the optimal assignment of s_a is recovered via $s_a = -\text{sgn}(P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}))$, unless $P(\mathbf{s}_{\text{nbr}}) = 0$, in which case s_a remains undetermined (leading to degeneracy).

The crucial step in the above procedure is converting $-|P(\mathbf{s})|$ into a multilinear polynomial $F(\mathbf{s})$. In the general case where $\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^d$, one can enumerate all 2^d configurations of \mathbf{s} and apply the *fast Walsh–Hadamard transform* (FWHT) [53]. Specifically, let $F(\mathbf{s}) = -|P(\mathbf{s})|$ and evaluate $F(\mathbf{s})$ for each $\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^d$. These values form a vector of length 2^d . The FWHT then computes all Walsh coefficients of F in $\mathcal{O}(d 2^d)$ time, which is more efficient than a naive $\mathcal{O}(2^{2d})$ approach that consists in solving a system of 2^d linear equations. Concretely, one labels each configuration \mathbf{s} by an integer $x \in \{0, \dots, 2^d - 1\}$, interprets x in binary, and places $F(\mathbf{s})$ in a vector f at index x . The FWHT proceeds through $\log_2(2^d) = d$ recursive stages, merging pairs $(f[i], f[j])$ by sum and difference in carefully structured blocks. Dividing the final (unnormalized) transform by 2^d yields the coefficients of the unique multilinear expansion of $-|P(\mathbf{s})|$. If P or $|P|$ has additional symmetry, one can exploit that to reduce computation further.

More generally, any real-valued function F on $\{\pm 1\}^d$ admits a unique multilinear representation

$$F(s_1, \dots, s_d) = \sum_{\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{1, \dots, d\}} c_{\mathcal{S}} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i,$$

and each coefficient c_S may be recovered either by an explicit summation

$$c_S = \frac{1}{2^d} \sum_{\sigma \in \{\pm 1\}^d} F(\sigma) \prod_{i \in S} \sigma_i,$$

or by the FWHT in $\mathcal{O}(d2^d)$ time. Setting $F(\mathbf{s}) = -|P(\mathbf{s})|$ then furnishes the required expansion for spin elimination. We obtain the final expression

$$-|P(\mathbf{s})| = -\frac{1}{2^d} \sum_{S \subseteq \{1, \dots, d\}} \left[\sum_{\sigma \in \{\pm 1\}^d} |P(\sigma)| \prod_{j \in S} \sigma_j \right] \prod_{j \in S} s_j. \quad (5)$$

In many settings, symmetry arguments or sparse connectivity may allow further simplifications. Next, we provide gadgets for spin elimination, emphasizing when eliminations can be especially helpful. In the Appendix, we illustrate the FWHT and provide a Mathematica code for calculating arbitrary multilinear expansion.

Two-spin gadget. Consider $P(s_b, s_c) = bs_b + cs_c$, where b, c are real coefficients. We use Eq. (5) and the symmetry of $|P|$ under $\mathbf{s} \mapsto -\mathbf{s}$ to find

$$-|bs_b + cs_c| = -\frac{1}{2} [|b+c| + |b-c| + s_b s_c (|b+c| - |b-c|)] \equiv F(s_b, s_c). \quad (6)$$

Therefore, if spin s_a was coupled to spin s_b with strength b and to spin s_c with strength c and not to other spins in the system, we can eliminate spin s_a by introducing the coupling of strength $(|b-c| - |b+c|)/2$ between s_b and s_c (or add this coupling to already existing coupling between these two spins). If the original Ising Hamiltonian is $H(\mathbf{s})$ with N spins we form the new Hamiltonian $H' = H - s_a P(s_b, s_c) + F(s_b, s_c)$ that has the same ground state as H but $N-1$ spins. Notice that the locality of H' is the same as H . If H has only 2-local interactions, then H' also has only 2-local interactions, so the Ising Hamiltonian remains quadratic after the spin elimination. Also, if s_b and s_c are neighbors in H , the degree remains the same or decreases in H' . Otherwise, both s_b and s_c increase their degrees by 1. If s_a also appears in H with a field as as_a , $P = a + bs_b + cs_c$ is no longer symmetric under $\mathbf{s} \mapsto -\mathbf{s}$ and the terms linear in s_b and s_c appear in H' . This is illustrated in Fig. 1(a). The gadget for spin elimination is

$$-|a + bs_b + cs_c| = A_2 + \alpha_2 s_b s_c + \beta_2 s_b + \gamma_2 s_c, \quad (7)$$

where $A_2 = -\sum_{i=0}^3 h_i$, $\alpha_2 = -h_0 + h_1 + h_2 - h_3$, $\beta_2 = h_0 + h_1 - h_2 - h_3$, $\gamma_2 = h_0 - h_1 + h_2 - h_3$. We introduced the notation $h_{\{\sigma_1 \sigma_0\}} = \frac{1}{4} |a + \sigma_1 b + \sigma_0 c|$, where $\sigma_0, \sigma_1 \in \{\pm 1\}$ and $\{\sigma_1 \sigma_0\}$ is written in the binary representation, e.g. $\sigma_1 = 1, \sigma_0 = -1$ corresponds to $\{\sigma_1 \sigma_0\} = 2$. Here, without loss of generality, we let $a \geq 0$.

Three-spin gadget. Many NP-hard Ising minimisation problems involve cubic graphs or subgraphs (weighted or unweighted). A useful gadget is, therefore, the one where s_a couples to exactly three neighbors (s_b, s_c, s_d) with weights b, c , and d , respectively. The spin s_a can again be eliminated without changing the locality of the Ising Hamiltonian but possibly changing the degrees of the neighbors. The term $s_a (bs_b + cs_c + ds_d)$ in the original Hamiltonian is replaced with $A_3 + \alpha_3 s_b s_c + \gamma_3 s_b s_d + \beta_3 s_c s_d$, where $A_3 = -\sum_{i=0}^3 g_i$, $\alpha_3 = g_0 + g_1 - g_2 - g_3$, $\beta_3 = -g_0 + g_1 + g_2 - g_3$, $\gamma_3 = g_0 - g_1 + g_2 - g_3$, where $g_{\{\sigma_1 \sigma_0\}} = \frac{1}{4} |b + \sigma_1 c + \sigma_0 d|$, $b \geq 0$. The corresponding gadget is depicted in Fig. 1(c) and takes the form

$$-|bs_b + cs_c + ds_d| = A_3 + \alpha_3 s_b s_c + \gamma_3 s_b s_d + \beta_3 s_c s_d. \quad (8)$$

k-local subgraphs. A notable case where coupling locality decreases upon spin elimination occurs when the coupling order matches the number of spins in the subgraph. Specifically,

if a spin s_a has $k - 1$ nearest neighbors and interacts with them through k -th order couplings, eliminating s_a reduces the coupling order to at most $k - 1$. This reduction happens because a k -th order interaction cannot be maintained by only $k - 1$ remaining spins. This effect is most clearly demonstrated in small subgraphs. Let s_a appear in the Hamiltonian as $as_a s_b s_c + bs_a s_b + cs_a s_c$. When spin s_a is eliminated, this term is replaced with

$$-|as_b s_c + bs_b + cs_c| = B + b' s_b + c' s_c + \alpha s_b s_c, \quad (9)$$

where $B = -\sum_{i=0}^3 h_i$ is the constant contribution to the Hamiltonian, the coupling between the remaining spins is given by $\alpha = -h_0 + h_1 + h_2 - h_3$, and the effective external fields acting on the remaining spins are $b' = h_0 - h_1 + h_2 - h_3$ and $c' = h_0 + h_1 - h_2 - h_3$. This transformation illustrates how eliminating a spin may reduce the order of interactions while introducing effective pairwise couplings and external fields acting on the remaining spins. Figures 1(b) and (d) depict the gadgets that eliminate spin s_a together with the highest local coupling (three in (b) and four in (d)).

n-spin symmetric gadget. In some applications, e.g. Ising Minimization on unweighted graphs or the memory recall we discuss below, the node s_a is connected to n other spins with the same coupling strength. In this case, we can also present a closed-form solution for spin elimination. We seek a multilinear polynomial representation of

$$F(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n) = -|s_1 + s_2 + \dots + s_n|.$$

Because flipping all spins $\mathbf{s} \mapsto -\mathbf{s}$ leaves F unchanged, only even-order products can appear in this expansion. Hence, we may write

$$F(s_1, \dots, s_n) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} c_{2k} \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\} \\ |\mathcal{S}|=2k}} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i,$$

where c_{2k} is the same for every subset \mathcal{S} of cardinality $2k$, and all coefficients of odd-order monomials vanish. To compute c_{2k} , we use the discrete Walsh transform:

$$c_{2k} = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^n} F(\mathbf{s}) \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i,$$

where \mathcal{S} is any fixed subset of size $2k$. Noting that $F(\mathbf{s}) = -|\sum_i s_i|$, we group configurations by the number j of spins equal to -1 . If exactly j spins are -1 , then $\sum_i s_i = n - 2j$, so $F(\mathbf{s}) = -|n - 2j|$, and there are $\binom{n}{j}$ ways to choose which j spins are negative. In these configurations, the factor $\prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i$ depends on how many of those $2k$ chosen spins lie in the negative set; if exactly r of the $2k$ spins in \mathcal{S} are -1 , the product contributes $(-1)^r$, and the number of ways to choose these r negatives within \mathcal{S} is $\binom{j}{r} \binom{n-j}{2k-r}$. Collecting all terms, including the factor $1/2^n$, and normalizing by the number of subsets in \mathcal{S} ($= \binom{n}{2k}$) one obtains

$$c_{2k} = \frac{1}{2^n \binom{n}{2k}} \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} [-|n - 2j|] \sum_{r=0}^{2k} \binom{j}{r} \binom{n-j}{2k-r} (-1)^r. \quad (10)$$

Putting everything together,

$$-|s_1 + s_2 + \dots + s_n| = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} c_{2k} \sum_{\substack{\mathcal{S} \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\} \\ |\mathcal{S}|=2k}} \prod_{i \in \mathcal{S}} s_i, \quad (11)$$

with c_{2k} given by Eq. (10). As a small illustration, for $n = 2$ we find $F(s_1, s_2) = -|s_1 + s_2| = -1 - s_1 s_2$. For $n = 3$, one obtains $F(s_1, s_2, s_3) = -|s_1 + s_2 + s_3| = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2}(s_1 s_2 + s_2 s_3 + s_1 s_3)$. For $n = 4$, the expansion is $F(s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) = -|s_1 + s_2 + s_3 + s_4| = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{A \subseteq \{1,2,3,4\} \\ |A|=2}} \prod_{i \in A} s_i + \frac{1}{2} s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4$.

Minimizing Ising Hamiltonians with couplings in $\{+1, -1, 0\}$ arises in a variety of NP-hard combinatorial optimization problems, such as the Kuratowskian formulation on graphs with edges in $\{+1, -1\}$, or in spin-glass models with $\pm 1, 0$ couplings [54]. Likewise, certain neural-network architectures (e.g. Hopfield networks or discrete Boltzmann machines) use quantized weights and reduce to the same $\{\pm 1, 0\}$ -valued Ising framework, where finding a low-energy configuration amounts to solving a similar NP-hard instance. Next, we introduce a gadget construction specifically tailored to handle these $\{\pm 1, 0\}$ couplings.

Multilinear expansion for $F(s_1, \dots, s_n) = -|\sigma_1 s_1 + \dots + \sigma_n s_n|$ with coefficients $\sigma_i \in \{\pm 1, 0\}$. Define new spins $t_i = \sigma_i s_i$. Then $t_i \in \{\pm 1\}$, and

$$F(s_1, \dots, s_n) = -|\sigma_1 s_1 + \dots + \sigma_n s_n| = -|t_1 + \dots + t_n|.$$

In terms of the t_i alone, we already know the unique multilinear expansion from Eqs. (10,11)

$$-|t_1 + t_2 + \dots + t_n| = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} c_{2k} \sum_{\substack{A \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\} \\ |A|=2k}} \prod_{i \in A} t_i. \quad (12)$$

where c_{2k} are the standard coefficients for the fully symmetric case Eqs. (10,11). Substitute back $t_i = \sigma_i s_i$ and use $\prod_{i \in S} t_i = \prod_{i \in S} (\sigma_i s_i) = \left(\prod_{i \in S} \sigma_i \right) \left(\prod_{i \in S} s_i \right)$. to get

$$-|\sigma_1 s_1 + \dots + \sigma_n s_n| = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor n/2 \rfloor} c_{2k} \sum_{\substack{S \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\} \\ |S|=2k}} \prod_{i \in S} \sigma_i \prod_{i \in S} s_i.$$

Only even subsets S appear, and each such S acquires the factor $\prod_{i \in S} \sigma_i$ multiplying c_{2k} .

Consider $F(s_1, s_2, s_3) = -|s_1 - s_2 + s_3|$. Here $n = 3$, $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3) = (1, -1, 1)$. We use the known symmetric expansion $-|t_1 + t_2 + t_3| = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2}(t_1 t_2 + t_2 t_3 + t_1 t_3)$ and substitute $(t_1, t_2, t_3) = (s_1, -s_2, s_3)$. Then

$$-|s_1 - s_2 + s_3| = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2}(s_1(-s_2) + (-s_2)s_3 + s_1 s_3) = -\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(s_1 s_2 + s_2 s_3 - s_1 s_3).$$

Consider $F(s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4) = -|s_1 - s_2 + s_3 - s_4|$. Here $n = 4$ and $\sigma = (1, -1, 1, -1)$. First recall that $-|t_1 + t_2 + t_3 + t_4| = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 4} t_i t_j + \frac{1}{2} t_1 t_2 t_3 t_4$. Substituting $t_1 = s_1, t_2 = -s_2, t_3 = s_3, t_4 = -s_4$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} -|s_1 - s_2 + s_3 - s_4| &= -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 4} (\sigma_i s_i)(\sigma_j s_j) + \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_1 s_1)(\sigma_2 s_2)(\sigma_3 s_3)(\sigma_4 s_4) \\ &= -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq 4} (\sigma_i \sigma_j)(s_i s_j) + \frac{1}{2} (\sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 \sigma_4)(s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4). \end{aligned}$$

Since $\sigma_1 \sigma_2 = -1, \sigma_2 \sigma_3 = -1, \sigma_1 \sigma_3 = +1$, etc., one can write out all pairwise products explicitly. This completes the derivation of the multilinear forms. More gadgets are given in the Appendix.

Fully coupled triplet. To illustrate the locality reduction, we consider the coupling of spin s_a with spins s_b and s_c via 2-body and 3-body coupling. To eliminate s_a we derived the multilinear expansion for $P(s_b, s_c) = -|a s_b s_c + b s_b + c s_c|$ that reads

$$-|a s_b s_c + b s_b + c s_c| = A + \beta s_b + \gamma s_c + \alpha s_b s_c, \quad (13)$$

Figure 1: Four gadgets for spin s_a elimination. (a) Left: Spin s_a is coupled to spin s_b with strength b and to spin s_c with strength c , while an external field of strength a acts on s_a (indicated by the yellow rectangle). Right: After eliminating s_a , spins s_b and s_c acquire an effective coupling of strength α and external fields of strengths β and γ . (b) Left: Spin s_a interacts with spins s_b and s_c through pairwise couplings of strengths b and c , as well as a three-body interaction of strength a . Right: After eliminating s_a , spins s_b and s_c acquire an effective two-body coupling of strength α and external fields (not shown). (c) Left: Spin s_a is coupled to spin s_b with strength b , to spin s_c with strength c , and to spin s_d with strength d . Right: After eliminating s_a , the remaining spins s_b , s_c , and s_d acquire effective pairwise couplings (α , β , γ). (d) Left: Spin s_a interacts with spins s_b , s_c , and s_d through pairwise couplings of strengths b , c , and d , respectively, along with three-body interactions among any three spins and a four-body interaction involving s_a , s_b , s_c , and s_d . Right: After eliminating s_a , the remaining spins s_b , s_c , and s_d acquire new two-body pairwise couplings and an effective three-body interaction. The expressions for the updated coupling strengths in cases (a–c) are provided in the main text.

where $A = -\sum_{i=0}^3 h_i$, $\beta = h_0 - h_1 + h_2 - h_3$, $\gamma = h_0 + h_1 - h_2 - h_3$, and $\alpha = -h_0 + h_1 + h_2 - h_3$. This gadget is depicted in Fig.1(b).

Finding a full solution to the problem. The following example demonstrates how spin elimination proceeds to the full solution in practice. Consider a k -local Hamiltonian:

$$H_I^{(0)} = s_1 s_2 + 2s_1 s_3 s_4 - s_1 s_4 s_5 + 3s_2 s_3 s_4 - s_3 s_4 s_5 + 2s_2 s_4 s_5 - s_3 s_5 + 3s_4 s_5 + s_2 s_3 + 2s_3 s_4 + s_1 s_5. \quad (14)$$

The spin s_1 appears in the local term $s_1(s_2 + 2s_3 s_4 + s_5 - s_4 s_5)$. To minimize $H_I^{(0)}$, set $s_1 = -\text{sign}(s_2 + 2s_3 s_4 + s_5 - s_4 s_5)$. Substituting the multilinear expansion from Eq. (5)

$$-|s_2 + 2s_3 s_4 + s_5 - s_4 s_5| = \frac{1}{4}(-9 - s_2 s_3 + s_4 - 3s_2 s_3 s_4 - s_2 s_5 + 3s_3 s_5 + s_2 s_4 s_5 - 3s_3 s_4 s_5) \quad (15)$$

yields a new Hamiltonian $H_I^{(1)}$ in (s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5) . Repeating this elimination for s_2 , s_3 , and s_4 gives

$$H_I^{(5)} = 2s_5 - 12,$$

whose minimum is -14 at $s_5 = -1$. Tracing backwards recovers the unique solution $s_4 = 1$, $s_3 = -1$, $s_2 = 1$, and $s_1 = 1$. The final ground state of $H_I^{(0)}$ remains intact, illustrating how dimension reduction preserves the essential solution structure.

In the next section, we consider how our approach is beneficial on a popular benchmark problem: the Maximum Cut problem.

3 Maximum cut problem on cubic graphs

The Maximum Cut (Max-Cut) problem serves as a central benchmark in combinatorial optimization, requiring the partition of a graph’s vertices into two sets to maximize the number of edges between them [55]. As an NP-hard problem, Max-Cut has attracted significant attention for evaluating emerging computational hardware, especially for 3-regular (cubic) graphs, in which every node has degree 3, [56, 57].

Recent experimental studies have explored diverse platforms for Max-Cut, including CIMs and the D-Wave quantum annealer, both of which have tackled instances up to 50 vertices [58]. Similarly, SBM achieves high-speed solutions via a bifurcation process on FPGA hardware [11], while D-Wave Advantage devices and D-Wave Hybrid workflows have been compared against SBM and classical simulated annealing for graphs with up to 10,000 nodes [59]. Other physical solvers that used Max-Cut on cubic graphs benchmarks include SPIMs [17, 18], as well as QAOA implementations on noisy intermediate-scale quantum (NISQ) devices, ranging from superconducting qubits [60] to Rydberg-atom simulators [61]. In particular, 3-regular graphs often require minimal embedding overhead on quantum annealers like D-Wave’s, as each logical node typically maps to a single qubit when the hardware degree exceeds 3. Comparative studies suggest that D-Wave can outperform optical CIMs on sparse cubic graphs [58], whereas CIMs show advantages on dense graphs. Notably, Max-Cut has also been utilized in benchmarking alternative physical computing approaches, including photonic recurrent Ising samplers based on oscillator-based annealers [62] and memristor-based architectures [63].

Our spin-elimination technique enables addressing 3-regular Max-Cut instances whose size exceeds the number of available physical spins. We can systematically remove spins while retaining the original ground-state solution by leveraging universal elimination gadgets in a polynomial-time procedure. Two principal strategies arise depending on the hardware’s interaction capabilities. (i) *Hardware Supporting Arbitrary k -local Interactions.* We partition the 3-regular graph into disjoint subgraphs of four neighbors each and eliminate one spin per subgraph using the gadget in Eq. (8). This ensures that the degrees of the surviving neighbors remain at most four, effectively removing about one-quarter of the spins in each round. In subsequent rounds, we form subgraphs of five spins, eliminate one spin, and introduce up to 4-local interactions. As the process continues, node degrees can increase accordingly, reaching up to $(2n + 2)$ after n rounds, with $(2n)$ -local couplings permitted and $3N/(n + 3)$ spins remaining. Figure 2(a) illustrates this approach, which trades dimensionality for interaction locality, eventually reaching the highest k -locality that the hardware can implement. (ii) *Hardware Restricted to Pairwise (2-local) Interactions.* Here, we cover the graph with overlapping subgraphs of four neighbors and eliminate every third node using the same gadget, Eq. (8). This approach preserves strictly 2-local interactions but causes some nodes to reach a degree of up to six, as shown in Figure 2(b). Nodes with degree 2 can arise in finite graphs, enabling further reduction via the gadget in Eqs. (6) or (7). By performing these elimination steps, we retain a fraction of the original spins; on average, more than one-third of the nodes can be removed for graphs, as shown in Fig. 3. An example of a 20-node cubic graph is shown in Figure 4, where 9 out of 20

spins are eliminated while the graph remains 2-local.

The practical implications of our technique are vast. For an Ising machine or quantum device that supports all-to-all 2-local couplings on N spins, our elimination technique makes it possible to solve 3-regular Max-Cut instances of size $\approx 3N/2$ on average. This is crucial for devices with strict qubit or spin limits, extending their effective capacity.

While CIMs have outperformed D-Wave on dense Max-Cut instances, they underperformed on 3-regular graphs [58]. Preprocessing with our spin-elimination method—reducing the graph while preserving its ground state means the CIM can tackle larger or effectively denser instances within the same spin budget. We, therefore, expect CIM to narrow (or even reverse) the performance gap against D-Wave on 3-regular Max-Cut.

In summary, our spin-elimination approach lets us adjust problem size and interaction order on the fly, enabling more scalable Max-Cut solutions on various Ising machines. Figures 2–4 illustrate key steps in the elimination procedure, visualizing how a 3-regular graph can be systematically pruned without compromising its ground state.

Figure 2: Spin-elimination strategies for Max-Cut on 3-regular (cubic) graphs. (a) k -local hardware: Start with disjoint subgraphs of four nodes (red outlines) and eliminate the central spin. This re-routes the surviving neighbors (magenta edges) to keep degree ≤ 4 , removing about one-quarter of the spins per round. Subsequent rounds can remove additional spins in subgraphs of five or more nodes, potentially introducing higher-order couplings as k increases. (b) 2-local hardware: Remove every third node in overlapping four-node subgraphs, boosting the maximum node degree to six but retaining strictly 2-local couplings.

4 Ising Hamiltonian on the J-Möbius Ladder

While 3-regular Max-Cut is already a stringent test for many solvers, the J -Möbius Ladder poses a particularly difficult challenge for soft-spin hardware platforms such as CIMs, SAWs, SBMs [57, 64]. In the J -Möbius Ladder of size N (with N divisible by 4), each vertex i

Figure 3: Degree distribution after spin elimination in Max-Cut problems on 3-regular graphs for different problem sizes $10 \leq N \leq 2^{13}$. Curves show the mean percentage of vertices ending with degree 0, 4, 5, or 6 after 10,000 independent elimination runs on graphs of size $N \leq 128$, 1,000 runs for $256 \leq N \leq 1024$, 100 runs for $N \geq 2048$. For every run the raw counts were first converted to a percentage of the original vertex total N ; the shaded bands depict ± 1 standard deviation of those per-run percentages. Because the spread of a proportion scales like $1/\sqrt{N}$, the bands tighten steadily with increasing system size. On average, over one-third of the nodes can be removed while controlling the increase in node degrees. The spread in the degree distribution is also shown.

connects to $i \pm 1 \pmod{N}$ and $i + N/2$, forming a ring with nearest-neighbor couplings of strength 1 and cross-ring couplings of strength J .

When the Ising Hamiltonian of this ladder is expressed in spin form, its ground state and first excited state are denoted by S_0 and S_1 . The state S_0 corresponds to perfect alternation around the ring, while S_1 flips two adjacent spins on opposite sides of the ladder with alternating spins in between. Which of these two states is the ground state depends on the value of J . If $J \leq 4/N$, then S_0 is the ground state; if $J > 4/N$, S_1 becomes energetically favored [64]. Soft-spin solvers often struggle in the regime $1 - \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{N}\right) < J < \frac{4}{N}$, because the primary eigenvector of the coupling matrix aligns with S_1 . During a bifurcation process, when soft spin amplitudes bifurcate from zero, these solvers initially converge to S_1 . Once spin's amplitudes reach ± 1 values, S_0 becomes energetically favored, but a large energy barrier separates S_0 and S_1 . Since half the spins must flip to transition between these two states, the system can easily become trapped in S_1 . An alternative approach has been to consider manifold reduction [64] or higher-dimensional spins, but this increases the total spin count from N to $3N$ [65].

Our spin-elimination technique reduces the dimensionality of the Möbius Ladder while allowing for higher node degree or higher-order interactions, thereby lowering the barrier between

Figure 4: Spin elimination for a cubic Max-Cut instance with $N = 20$. Nine out of 20 spins are eliminated in the order 0, 1, 4, 6, 7, 8, 12, 13, 3 the upper left to the lower right. Antiferromagnetic couplings appear in black; ferromagnetic couplings in red.

\mathbf{S}_0 and \mathbf{S}_1 . This makes it easier for soft-spin or quantum-inspired devices to access the correct ground state. To illustrate, consider $N = 8$, with the initial Hamiltonian

$$H_M^{(0)} = s_1 s_2 + s_1 s_8 + s_2 s_3 + s_3 s_4 + s_4 s_5 + s_5 s_6 + s_6 s_7 + s_7 s_8 + J(s_1 s_5 + s_2 s_6 + s_3 s_7 + s_4 s_8). \quad (16)$$

By eliminating spins 1, 3, and 6 using the procedure described in Section 3, the resulting 2-local Hamiltonian becomes

$$H_M^{(3)} = -3 - s_2 s_4 + s_4 s_5 - s_5 s_7 - s_2 s_8 + s_7 s_8 - \frac{1}{2}J(-3 + s_2 s_4 - 2s_2 s_5 - 2s_2 s_7 - s_4 s_7 + s_5 s_7 + s_2 s_8 + 2s_4 s_8 - s_5 s_8). \quad (17)$$

Figure 5 enumerates the energy states before and after elimination. The states corresponding to \mathbf{S}_0 and \mathbf{S}_1 remain the lowest-energy configurations, with higher-energy states effectively pruned. The resulting Hamiltonian retains the correct ground-state properties but simplifies the energy landscape in a manner that aids soft-spin or quantum-inspired devices. In particular, smaller or cluster-based spin flips become sufficient to transition to \mathbf{S}_0 , thereby overcoming the large barrier separating \mathbf{S}_0 and \mathbf{S}_1 . Compared to approaches that embed spins in higher dimensions [65], this method does not inflate the total number of spins and instead removes them while preserving the exact ground state.

Further elimination introduces higher-order interactions. Notably, the elimination keeps track of all solution branches. In our example considered above for $N = 8$, after eliminating spins 8, 2, and 4, the new Hamiltonian is

$$H_M^{(6)} = \begin{cases} -4 - 4J, & \text{if } J \geq \frac{1}{2}, \\ -6 + (2J - 1)s_5 s_7, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

which correctly recovers the critical value $J = \frac{1}{2}$. For $J \leq \frac{1}{2}$, minimizing $H_M^{(6)}$ requires $s_5 s_7 = 1$, which back-maps to \mathbf{S}_0 . For $J \geq \frac{1}{2}$, the energy no longer depends on s_5 or s_7 , increasing degeneracy in the ground state and reproducing \mathbf{S}_1 .

Figure 5: The distribution of the energy values for $N = 8$ in the Möbius Ladder instance. In (a), the full Hamiltonian $H_M^{(0)}$ is enumerated; in (b), three spins are eliminated, giving $H_M^{(3)}$. The ground and first-excited states remain essentially the same, while higher-energy states are pruned. Light orange marks the ground and the first excited states.

5 Associative memory and Hopfield networks

Spin elimination strongly influences machine learning and memory retrieval, especially within energy-based architectures such as Boltzmann machines [66] and Hopfield networks [67]. A Boltzmann machine defines a probability distribution $\text{Prob}(s) \propto \exp(-E(s))$, where the energy function $E(s)$ is the Ising Hamiltonian, with binary units treated as spins and connection weights as couplings. Restricted Boltzmann machines (RBMs) are known to be universal approximators of discrete probability distributions in the sense that they can approximate any target distribution arbitrarily well, given sufficient hidden units [68]. Pruning methods for reducing hidden units in RBMs or general neural networks have been investigated, aiming to preserve performance while diminishing complexity [69, 70]. Analogously, incorporating higher-order interactions can yield more expressive inference or learning models: eliminating certain spins while permitting higher-order couplings among the remaining ones should allow a Boltzmann machine to capture intricate dependencies with fewer total spins, thereby achieving a more compact yet powerful representation [70].

Hopfield networks, in particular, benefit from higher-order interactions. Recent memristor-based implementations show that such higher-order Hopfield dynamics improve performance on tasks like satisfiability (SAT), compared with purely pairwise networks [32, 33]. Similar gains may arise in Ising-based deep learning frameworks, where constraints or objectives are encoded as high-order energy terms.

Another promising direction is to apply spin elimination for memory retrieval in Hopfield networks, which function as symmetric Ising models storing patterns as global energy minima [67]. Retrieving a memory involves starting from a perturbed or partial pattern and letting the network relax to a low-energy attractor that ideally corresponds to a stored configuration. Modern dense associative memories employ higher-order terms to expand capacity beyond classical Hopfield limits [71, 72], and one can, in principle, remove redundant units while preserving essential attractors. Quantum Hopfield models have also been proposed, further suggesting the breadth of potential applications [73].

In the discrete Hopfield model, each neuron is a spin $s_i \in \{\pm 1\}$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$, and one seeks to store p patterns $\{\xi^\mu\}_{\mu=1}^p$ in such a way that each ξ^μ becomes (along with its negative) a

global minimum. The classical Hebbian prescription assigns

$$J_{ij} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\mu=1}^p \xi_i^\mu \xi_j^\mu \quad \text{for } i \neq j, \quad J_{ii} = 0,$$

leading to the energy

$$E(\mathbf{s}) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} s_i s_j. \quad (19)$$

If the stored patterns $\{\xi^\mu\}$ are mutually orthogonal, each ξ^μ becomes a stable attractor without introducing additional mixed states. However, Hopfield retrieval is commonly implemented in a continuous dynamical system where each neuron has a real-valued internal variable x_i and an output $y_i = \tanh(x_i)$. The typical dynamics follow

$$\tau \dot{x}_i = -x_i + \sum_j J_{ij} \tanh(x_j),$$

with a Lyapunov function

$$E(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} J_{ij} y_i y_j + \frac{1}{2} \sum_i [x_i y_i - \ln(1 + y_i^2)]. \quad (20)$$

Even if the underlying binary patterns are orthogonal, the continuous system often acquires additional stable equilibria. These spurious attractors do not correspond to any stored pattern, as neurons can converge to intermediate values between ± 1 .

While each ξ^μ ideally becomes a stable fixed point, classical Hopfield networks have a limited capacity (on the order of $0.14 N$, [74]). Dense associative memories address these limitations by replacing the pairwise term $\sum_{i \neq j} J_{ij} s_i s_j$ (or its continuous analogue) with higher-order interactions [71]. One stores $\{\xi^\mu\}_{\mu=1}^p$ by defining a rank- k tensor

$$J_{i_1, \dots, i_k} = \frac{1}{N^{k-1}} \sum_{\mu=1}^p \xi_{i_1}^\mu \dots \xi_{i_k}^\mu,$$

and writing a corresponding energy that naturally enables larger capacity and fewer spurious minima. Empirical results show that such dense (higher-order) Hopfield networks can store many more patterns than classical ones and converge more reliably from random initial states [72].

A primary question, then, is whether spin elimination can simultaneously preserve the large capacity afforded by higher-order models and restrict the system to only 2-local interactions or at least to a lower-order k -local form. We illustrate this possibility with a two-bit ripple-carry adder, a fundamental digital circuit [75]. In such a system, there is an intermediate carry bit that cannot be written as a direct function of the other spins alone, illustrating the genuinely multi-step logical structure that higher-order interactions can capture. Consider eight spins $\{s_1, s_2, s_3, s_4, s_5, s_6, s_7, s_8\}$. Interpret (s_1, s_2) as the first two-bit number, (s_3, s_4) as the second two-bit number, and set an input carry spin $s_9 = -1$ (which corresponds to logical 0). The lower adder takes inputs (s_2, s_4, s_9) and produces sum bit s_6 and intermediate carry s_5 . The upper adder then takes inputs (s_1, s_3, s_5) and yields sum bit s_7 and final carry s_8 . Each full-adder constraint can be written in terms of multilinear Ising interactions that vanish only if the correct sum and carry are produced. One obtains a Hamiltonian,

$$H_a^{(0)} = (s_6 - s_2 s_4 s_9)^2 + (s_5 - T(s_2, s_4, s_9))^2 + (s_7 - s_1 s_3 s_5)^2 + (s_8 - T(s_1, s_3, s_5))^2, \quad (21)$$

where $T(a, b, c) = \frac{1}{2}[(a + b + c) - abc]$ and $s_9 = -1$. This formulation encodes the entire space of valid two-bit additions, resulting in 16 ground states. Expanded, the Hamiltonian reveals various two-body and four-body terms, and crucially, no single spin can be written purely as a closed-form multilinear function of the others (for instance, s_5 depends on $\{s_2, s_4, s_9\}$ but also influences the second adder).

We then perform spin elimination on $\{s_1, \dots, s_4\}$ in successive steps; see the Appendix for details. Each eliminated spin is substituted with an effective expression in terms of its neighbors using derived gadgets, systematically reducing the number of variables while introducing or reshaping interactions. Remarkably, after four such eliminations, we obtain a purely pairwise Hamiltonian in the four remaining spins

$$H_a^{(4)} = 2 + s_6 + s_5(1 + s_6 - s_7 - s_8) + s_7 s_8,$$

yet the network still exhibits 16 valid minima corresponding to all two-bit sums. In principle, this approach could enable extremely high-capacity associative memories using only pairwise interactions, provided that the recovery expressions for eliminated spins are memorized.

Eliminating spins or adding hidden spins have previously been proposed by approximate techniques that can create many unintended local minima if the constraints are not tightly calibrated [76]. In Hopfield embeddings of error-correcting codes (e.g., Hamming codes), single-bit errors can draw the network into spurious attractors since local update rules may flip an incorrect bit rather than the truly erroneous one, preventing convergence to a valid codeword. An expander-based design in [76] circumvented this by making deviations from each stored pattern systematically raise the energy, guiding the system toward the correct attractor. Thus, merely achieving a large theoretical capacity is insufficient; one must also ensure the basins of attraction are suitably shaped for robust retrieval. Our approach does not suffer from this problem as the exactness of the procedure preserves global minima and their degeneracies. It is equally important to handle spurious states that can appear in such reorganized networks. If elimination or bipartite mapping is not carefully tuned, new local minima can emerge. Our exact spin elimination instead reduces the number of spurious states since our technique simplifies the energy landscape without losing correct attractors.

If hardware allows for k -local interactions, we do not have to reduce the dimensionality all the way up to 2-local interactions. Our spin elimination can help transform a classical Hopfield network into one with higher-order interactions, albeit distinct from earlier dense memory frameworks [71]. A thorough exploration of how specific elimination strategies alter capacity and spurious states remains an open question, though we provide a simple example with $N = 32$ spins storing $p = 4$ orthogonal patterns. Before elimination, this 32-spin continuous system has 20 distinct global and local minima, ranging from energy -16 (global) to 26 as shown in Fig. 6. After removing four spins (one per subgroup) using the gadget on Eq. (11) and allowing up to 6-local couplings, the network is left with 15 minima from -16 to 12 , effectively eliminating several high-lying local minima and doubling the frequency of correctly recovering the planted pattern in random trials. Figure 6 illustrates the distribution of minima and their frequencies (that represent the "volume" of the attractors) before (main figure) and after (inset) another two spins from each group are eliminated.

In summary, removing spins can speed up convergence and allow larger memories to be handled or eliminate spurious local minima in both Hopfield and dense memory networks. The spin elimination technique we introduced maintains the global minima and preserves the degeneracy. So, simplifying the energy landscape by decreasing the dimension removes the local minima or spurious states and facilitates the recall of the stored patterns. By removing spins from the Hopfield memory network, one introduces the higher-order terms, bridging between

Hopfield and dense networks. However, one gets a network different from the dense associative memory networks previously introduced [71]. This is beneficial for locality-restricted hardware: one starts with dense memory capable of storing the maximum number of patterns and performs spin elimination, reaching the limit on the k -locality of the hardware while keeping the memories stored.

Figure 6: Frequencies of obtaining the minima of the Hopfield energy given by Eq.(19) for $N = 32$ (main figure) and after 12 spins were eliminated (inset). 10,000 initial conditions were considered for each coupling matrix J_{ij} . The system evolves according to gradient descent $\dot{x}_i = -\partial E/\partial x_i$ with $E(\mathbf{x})$ given by Eq. (20). At the fixed point, the values are clamped by $s_i = \text{sgn}(\tanh(x_i))$, and the Ising energy of Eq. (19) is calculated. The orange bar corresponds to the ground state.

6 Factorization

Integer factorization is a central problem in computational number theory, underpinning the security of RSA encryption [77]. Although Shor’s algorithm offers an exponential quantum speedup, its practical realization remains challenging due to the extensive qubit counts and stringent error-correction demands [78]. Consequently, hybrid classical-quantum approaches have emerged for near-term quantum devices, seeking to reduce resource requirements while still leveraging quantum speedups. Recent advances in superconducting processors have facilitated factorization experiments via variational methods such as QAOA [79, 80]. One early milestone was the factorization of 291311 using an NMR-based adiabatic protocol with only three qubits [81]. More recently, a ten-qubit superconducting device achieved the factorization of a 48-bit integer, underscoring the scalability of sublinear-resource approaches [82].

In these approaches, factorization is reformulated as an optimization problem rather than relying on the direct integer representation in Shor’s method, substantially reducing qubit counts.

Specifically, the resource scaling can be approximated by $O(m/\log m)$, where m is the bit-length of the integer to be factored, reflecting the smoothness-lattice interplay in the algorithm [82]. This technique was claimed to be the most qubit-efficient method for factorization to date, wherein the problem Hamiltonian arises from Babai's nearest-plane algorithm [83] and is mapped to quantum spin operators for iterative QAOA optimization. For extremely large integers, however, compiling or reducing the resulting Hamiltonian to a handful of qubits could itself become prohibitively time-consuming; it remains to be seen whether this lattice-based method can be extended efficiently and practically at much larger scales.

In any case, our spin-elimination framework enables a further reduction in qubit usage. As an illustration, we show that the three-qubit factorization of 291311 from [81] can be compressed to two qubits, and the ten-qubit factorization of a 48-bit integer in [82] can be reduced to three or even two qubits. Consider the factorization $N = 291311 = p \times q$. Labeling the unknown factors in binary as

$$p = \{1 p_m p_{m-1} \dots p_2 p_1 1\}, \quad q = \{1 q_n q_{n-1} \dots q_2 q_1 1\},$$

with each factor thus constrained by $\sum 2^i$ terms. After solving a set of linear relationships, the factorization of $N = 291311$ reduces to the Ising Hamiltonian

$$H_p = (q_1 + q_2 - 2 q_1 q_2 - 1)^2 + (q_2 + q_5 - 2 q_2 q_5)^2 + (q_1 + q_5 - 2 q_1 q_5 - 1)^2, \quad (22)$$

where one possible factor is $q = \{1000 q_5 01 q_2 q_1 1\}$. Mapping each binary variable to a qubit operator via $q_i = (1 - \sigma_z^i)/2$, for $i = 1, 2, 5$, the Ising Hamiltonian can be written as

$$H_{3p} = \frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(s_1 s_2 + s_1 s_3 - s_2 s_3), \quad (23)$$

where $s_i = \pm 1$ correspond to σ_z^i . We then eliminate s_1 by enforcing $s_1 \rightarrow -\text{sgn}(s_2 + s_3)$ and rewriting $-|s_2 + s_3|$ as multilinear polynomial using the gadget in Eq. (6) or in Eq. (11). This results in a two-qubit Hamiltonian

$$H_{2p} = 1 - s_2 s_3,$$

which indicates that the ground state satisfies $s_2 = s_3$, implying s_1 is opposite in sign. When mapped back to binary form, this yields $\{1000001011\}$ or $\{1000101101\}$ as factors of 291311, corresponding to 523 and 557.

Similarly, the ten-qubit Hamiltonian

$$\begin{aligned} H_c^{10} &= 22\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^2 + 16\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^3 + 8\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^4 - 14\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^5 + 8\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^6 + 4\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^7 - 8\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^8 - 10\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^9 - 22\sigma_z^1\sigma_z^{10} \\ &- 46\sigma_z^2 - 14\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^3 + 20\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^4 + 14\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^5 - 12\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^6 + 2\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^7 - 24\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^8 - 28\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^9 + 2\sigma_z^2\sigma_z^{10} \\ &- 16\sigma_z^3 - 18\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^4 + 10\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^5 + 36\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^6 + 12\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^7 + 16\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^8 + 6\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^9 - 30\sigma_z^3\sigma_z^{10} - 78\sigma_z^3 \\ &+ 28\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^5 - 26\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^6 + 10\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^7 + 10\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^8 + 16\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^9 - 4\sigma_z^4\sigma_z^{10} - 72\sigma_z^4 + 10\sigma_z^5\sigma_z^6 + 24\sigma_z^5\sigma_z^7 \\ &+ 20\sigma_z^5\sigma_z^8 + 12\sigma_z^5\sigma_z^9 - 8\sigma_z^5\sigma_z^{10} - 116\sigma_z^5 - 8\sigma_z^6\sigma_z^7 + 22\sigma_z^6\sigma_z^8 - 6\sigma_z^6\sigma_z^9 - 36\sigma_z^6\sigma_z^{10} - 12\sigma_z^6 \\ &- 16\sigma_z^7\sigma_z^8 + 16\sigma_z^7\sigma_z^9 + 20\sigma_z^7\sigma_z^{10} - 84\sigma_z^7 + 34\sigma_z^8\sigma_z^9 - 42\sigma_z^8\sigma_z^{10} - 36\sigma_z^8 + 18\sigma_z^9\sigma_z^{10} - 74\sigma_z^9 \\ &- 24\sigma_z^{10} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

(from [82]) can be systematically reduced. For instance, the coefficient of $\sigma_z^1 = s_1$ in H_c^{10} is

$$C_{s_1} = -46 - 22 s_{10} + 22 s_2 + 16 s_3 + 8 s_4 - 14 s_5 + 8 s_6 + 4 s_7 - 8 s_8 - 10 s_9.$$

Substituting $s_1 C_{s_1} \rightarrow -|C_{s_1}|$ in its multilinear form, one eliminates s_1 while leaving a multilinear polynomial in the remaining spins. Repeating this for s_2, s_3, \dots successively yields a final cubic Hamiltonian

$$H_c = -405 - 52 s_{10} - 11 s_8 - 18 s_{10} s_8 - 25 s_9 + 16 s_{10} s_9 + 19 s_8 s_9 + 8 s_{10} s_8 s_9.$$

One can then either quadratize [30, 38] or further eliminate spins (e.g. s_8), ultimately obtaining

$$H_c = -425 - 61 s_{10} - 15 s_9 + 33 s_{10} s_9,$$

which depends only on two spins. Minimizing this two-spin Hamiltonian recovers the same ground state as the ten-qubit version (which is (0100010010) or, in terms of the spins of the Ising Hamiltonian (1, -1, 1, , 1, 1, 1, -1, 1, 1, -1, 1) where again we associate spins s_i with σ_z^i), thus identifying the integer’s prime factors. The order of elimination steps does not affect the final solution. By applying spin elimination, one can effectively reduce qubit requirements from ten to two, enabling factorization with a substantially smaller hardware footprint. In more general settings, this approach can be extended to larger integers, potentially pushing record-breaking factorizations on near-term devices. Although merely decreasing the spin count does not guarantee a quantum advantage, it constitutes a crucial engineering step toward feasible QAOA-based factorization, lowering circuit depth and reducing vulnerability to noise. As hardware scales, balancing the time and complexity required to reduce the Hamiltonian against the benefits of a smaller qubit count will be critical. Whether the overall lattice-based strategy remains efficient for significantly larger integers is an open question, one whose resolution will be central to future progress in practical quantum factorization.

7 Conclusions and Outlook

We have presented an exact spin-elimination technique for Ising Hamiltonians that can remove individual spins in either a single step or through a systematic, repeated procedure. By replacing each eliminated spin with an appropriate higher-order interaction (a “gadget”), the approach preserves the ground-state configurations of the original system without introducing auxiliary spins. In this way, it balances strict correctness and practical efficiency, directly lowering the total spin count while retaining crucial low-energy properties. The resulting trade-off of the reduced dimensionality at the cost of higher-order couplings or increased degree is especially beneficial for hardware platforms that support multi-body interactions or all-to-all connectivity but face limitations in qubit or spin resources.

In our demonstrations, this technique enables significantly larger 3-regular Max-Cut instances to be tackled without exceeding 2-local hardware constraints, reduces the qubit requirements for QAOA-based factorization of sizable integers, allows for a novel increase in memory capacity, and mitigates spurious attractors in Hopfield networks, thereby improving memory recall.

Several directions emerge from this research:

- (1) **Locality-limited decimation.** By controlling the order of interactions introduced during spin elimination, one can ensure hardware compatibility where only up to k -body terms are permissible. Future gadget constructions might better exploit sparse couplings or structured matrices, simplifying the resulting Hamiltonians.

- (2) **Hybrid workflows.** Spin elimination could be integrated into iterative pre-processing pipelines that alternate with partial variable-fixing or sampling. Such hybrid classical-quantum strategies would adaptively compress larger systems to fit onto emerging quantum or analog hardware.
- (3) **Scaling to large instances.** As hardware resources and problem sizes grow, preprocessing steps analogous to those in modern SAT solvers or integer programming could become standard. Detecting spins whose elimination or assignment causes minimal overhead, then progressively reducing the Hamiltonian, might substantially extend the feasible problem scale.
- (4) **Advanced machine learning architectures.** The technique can be leveraged to maintain high capacity in energy-based models while lowering computational or hardware costs. This trade-off is already apparent in dense Hopfield networks, but further exploration is needed on how to best preserve stable memory states while consolidating or eliminating spins.

Ultimately, exact spin elimination offers a versatile tool for bridging the gap between small-scale demonstrations and large-scale optimization and machine learning applications. By systematically reducing problem dimensions while keeping ground-state configurations, it paves the way for more efficient use of specialized hardware and scalable quantum-classical algorithms. As these techniques mature, they may prove as integral to future Ising-based solvers and quantum-classical workflows as preprocessing has become in modern SAT and integer programming solvers, thereby helping push the frontier of solvable problem sizes on next-generation devices.

Finally, these results underscore that next-generation physical spin machines should be able to implement arbitrary, multi-body couplings. By focusing on hardware natively realising multi-body couplings, we can exploit exact spin elimination to systematically condense problems into those with fewer spins without sacrificing essential low-energy properties.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Example of the Fast Walsh-Hadamard Transform

In this section, we apply the fast Walsh-Hadamard Transform to calculate the multilinear polynomial to represent $P(\mathbf{s}) = -|s_1 + s_2 + s_3|$ used, for instance, for Max-Cut of cubic graph problems. Consider the function $P(s_1, s_2, s_3) = -|s_1 + s_2 + s_3|$, where each s_i takes values in $\{+1, -1\}$. To derive its multilinear polynomial representation via the Walsh-Hadamard transform, we first list all points (s_1, s_2, s_3) in $\{\pm 1\}^3$. A convenient labeling convention indexes these eight points by the integers 0 through 7, encoding each integer i in binary as $(i_2 i_1 i_0)$. In this convention, $(i_2 i_1 i_0) = (0, 0, 0)$ corresponds to $(s_1, s_2, s_3) = (+1, +1, +1)$, $(0, 0, 1)$ corresponds to $(+1, +1, -1)$, and so on, up to $(1, 1, 1)$ for $(-1, -1, -1)$. Evaluating P at each

of these points yields the eight values $[-3, -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, -1, -3]$, which we arrange in a vector F . The standard unnormalized Walsh–Hadamard transform of this 8-element vector is computed through a sequence of pairwise “sum and difference” merges. In the first stage, we partition F into four pairs, replace each pair (x, y) by $(x + y, x - y)$, and repeat this procedure on blocks of increasing size until we merge all eight entries. After the first merge (size 2 merges) we get $F = [-4, -2, -2, 0, -2, 0, 4, 2]$, after the second merge (size 4 merges) $F = [-6, -2, -2, -2, -6, 2, 2, -2]$. After size 8 merge we get the final transformed vector as $F = [-12, 0, 0, -4, 0, -4, -4, 0]$. To convert these unnormalized transform values into the actual multilinear coefficients c_α , we divide by $2^3 = 8$, giving $[-1.5, 0, 0, -0.5, 0, -0.5, -0.5, 0]$. Each position in this length-8 result corresponds to a subset $\alpha \subseteq \{1, 2, 3\}$, again following the binary indexing convention in which the integer $i = (i_2 i_1 i_0)$ denotes the subset containing j if and only if $i_{j-1} = 1$. In particular, index 0 (binary $(0, 0, 0)$) corresponds to the empty subset and thus the constant term -1.5 ; index 1 (binary $(0, 0, 1)$) corresponds to the subset $\{1\}$ and thus the coefficient of s_1 ; index 3 (binary $(0, 1, 1)$) corresponds to $\{1, 2\}$ and thus the coefficient of $s_1 s_2$, and so on. Collecting these coefficients, we see that the unique multilinear polynomial matching P on all of $\{\pm 1\}^3$ is

$$P(s_1, s_2, s_3) = -\frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{2} s_1 s_2 - \frac{1}{2} s_1 s_3 - \frac{1}{2} s_2 s_3. \quad (25)$$

The efficiency of this process arises from the Walsh–Hadamard transform, which evaluates or inverts the entire set of function values and coefficients in time $O(N 2^N)$.

8.2 Mathematica Code for Constructing a Multilinear Polynomial

This Mathematica code constructs the unique multilinear polynomial $G(\mathbf{s})$, that coincides with the function $F : \{\pm 1\}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. For brevity, we denote $[n] = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. For each subset $\alpha \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$, define

$$c_\alpha = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^n} F(\mathbf{s}) \prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i.$$

The code outputs

$$G(s_1, \dots, s_n) = \sum_{\alpha \subseteq [n]} c_\alpha \prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i,$$

which is unique and satisfies $G(\mathbf{s}) = F(\mathbf{s})$ for all $\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^n$. This polynomial is multilinear in the variables s_1, \dots, s_n , since every monomial is of the form $\prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i$ with no repeated factors and no power higher than 1.

```
spinConfigs[n_] := Tuples[{-1, 1}, n];
```

spinConfigs[n_] returns a list of all possible spin configurations in $\{\pm 1\}^n$.

$$\text{spinConfigs}[n] = \{(s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n) \mid s_i \in \{-1, 1\}\}.$$

```
allSubsets[n_] :=
```

```
  Flatten[Table[Subsets[Range[n], {k}], {k, 0, n}], 1];
```

allSubsets[n_] produces all subsets of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, arranged in ascending order by size (0 through n) and then lexicographically. Symbolically, it returns

$$\{\alpha : \alpha \subseteq [n]\}.$$

```
monomial[s_List, alpha_List] := Times @@ (s[[#]] & /@ alpha);
```

For a given spin configuration $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$ and subset $\alpha \subseteq [n]$, `monomial[s, alpha]` implements $\prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i$.

$$\text{monomial}(s, \alpha) = \prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i.$$

```
coefficientForSubset[F_, alpha_List, configs_List] :=
Module[{n},
  n = Length[configs[[1]]];
  (1/2^n)*Total[Table[
    F[configs[[j]]]*monomial[configs[[j]], alpha],
    {j, 1, Length[configs]}]]];
```

`coefficientForSubset[F, alpha, configs]` computes the coefficient c_α for the subset α by summing over all configurations $\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^n$. Mathematically,

$$c_\alpha = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{\mathbf{s} \in \{\pm 1\}^n} F(\mathbf{s}) \prod_{i \in \alpha} s_i.$$

Here, `configs` is the list of all \mathbf{s} in $\{\pm 1\}^n$, so the code sums $F(\mathbf{s}) \times \text{monomial}(\mathbf{s}, \alpha)$ over all \mathbf{s} , then normalizes by $\frac{1}{2^n}$.

```
FindMultilinearPolynomial[F_, n_] :=
Module[{configs, subs, coeffs, poly}, configs = spinConfigs[n];
  subs = allSubsets[n];
  coeffs =
    Table[coefficientForSubset[F, subs[[k]], configs], {k, 1,
      Length[subs]}];
  poly = 0;
  Do[With[{alpha = subs[[k]], c = coeffs[[k]]},
    poly += c*Product[Symbol["s" <> ToString[i]], {i, alpha}], {k,
    1, Length[subs]}];
  Return[<|"Subsets" -> subs, "Coefficients" -> coeffs,
    "Polynomial" -> poly|>];];
```

`FindMultilinearPolynomial[F, n_]` is the main function that builds the complete list `configs` of spin configurations using `spinConfigs[n]` and forms the list `subs` of all subsets of $\{1, \dots, n\}$. For each subset α , it calculates c_α using `coefficientForSubset[F, alpha, configs]`. Finally, it constructs a symbolic polynomial in the formal variables $s[1], s[2], \dots, s[n]$:

$$\text{poly} = \sum_{\alpha \subseteq [n]} \left(c_\alpha \prod_{i \in \alpha} s[i] \right),$$

where `poly` is stored together with the subset list and coefficient list. The example of usage is for the gadget used above for $F(\mathbf{s}) = -|s_1 + s_2 + s_3|$. The commands

```
F3[s_List] := -Abs[ s[[1]] + s[[2]] + s[[3]] ];
res = FindMultilinearPolynomial[F3, 3]
```

return the result as

```

<|"Subsets" -> {{}, {1}, {2}, {3}, {1, 2}, {1, 3}, {2, 3}, {1, 2, 3}},
  "Coefficients" -> {-(3/2), 0, 0, 0, -(1/2), -(1/2), -(1/2), 0},
  "Polynomial" -> -(3/2) - (s1 s2)/2 - (s1 s3)/2 - (s2 s3)/2|>

```

The resulting polynomial coincides with Eq. (25).

8.3 Useful gadgets

Here, we present two more gadgets that appear in various contexts.

Two-body gadgets. The multilinear form of

$$-|a s_1 s_2 + b s_1 s_3 + c s_2 + d s_3| = A + \alpha s_1 + \beta s_2 s_3 + \gamma s_1 s_2 s_3, \quad (26)$$

where $a \geq 0$, $A = -h_2 - h_4 - h_7 - h_1$, $\alpha = -h_2 + h_4 - h_7 + h_1$, $\beta = h_2 - h_4 - h_7 + h_1$, and $\gamma = h_2 + h_4 - h_7 - h_1$. Here, as in the main text and below, we used the binary definition of the indexes so that $h_{\{\sigma_2 \sigma_1 \sigma_0\}} = \frac{1}{4}|a + \sigma_2 b + \sigma_1 c + \sigma_0 d|$ and $\{\sigma_2 \sigma_1 \sigma_0\}$ is the binary representation of decimal subscripts.

Three-body gadgets. The multilinear form of

$$-|a s_1 s_2 s_3 + b s_1 s_2 s_4 + c s_3 + d s_4| = A + \alpha s_1 s_2 + \beta s_3 s_4 + \gamma s_1 s_2 s_3 s_4, \quad (27)$$

with the same values of A, α, β, γ as above.

8.4 Two-bit ripple-carry adder details

We expand the Hamiltonian given in Eq. (21) of the main text, drop the constant offsets (since $(\pm 1)^2 = 1$) and write the simplified Ising Hamiltonian as

$$\begin{aligned}
H_a^{(0)} = & -2 s_6 s_2 s_4 s_9 - s_5 \left[(s_2 + s_4 + s_9) - s_2 s_4 s_9 \right] \\
& -2 s_7 s_1 s_3 s_5 - s_8 \left[(s_1 + s_3 + s_5) - s_1 s_3 s_5 \right].
\end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

We eliminate s_1 by replacing $s_1 \left(-2 s_3 s_5 s_7 - s_8 + s_3 s_5 s_8 \right)$ with the right-hand side of the gadget in Eq. (27) with $a = 2, b = -1, c = 0, d = 1$, while renumbering $\{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with $\{3, 5, 7, 8\}$. When the optimal values of s_3, s_5, s_7, s_8 will be obtained we will assign

$$s_1 \rightarrow -\text{sign}\left(-2 s_3 s_5 s_7 - s_8 + s_3 s_5 s_8\right),$$

The Hamiltonian becomes

$$H_a^{(1)} = 6 + s_5 - s_2 s_5 - s_4 s_5 - s_2 s_4 s_5 + 2 s_2 s_4 s_6 - s_3 s_8 - s_5 s_8 + s_7 s_8 - s_3 s_5 s_7 s_8.$$

After eliminating s_2 by using the gadget in Eq. (26) for $a = 1, b = -2, c = 1, d = 0$, so that $s_2 \rightarrow -\text{sign}\left(-s_5 - s_4 s_5 + 2 s_4 s_6\right)$, we get

$$H_a^{(2)} = 4 + s_5 - s_4 s_5 + s_5 s_6 + s_4 s_5 s_6 - s_3 s_8 - s_5 s_8 + s_7 s_8 - s_3 s_5 s_7 s_8. \quad (29)$$

After eliminating s_3 using the gadget in Eq. (27), so that

$$s_3 \rightarrow -\text{sign}\left(-s_8 - s_5 s_7 s_8\right),$$

we get

$$H_a^{(3)} = 3 + s_5 \left(1 + s_4 (-1 + s_6) + s_6 - s_7 - s_8 \right) + s_7 s_8.$$

And, finally, eliminating s_4 , $s_4 \rightarrow -\text{sign}(-s_5 + s_5 s_6)$ brings about the quadratic form

$$H_a^{(4)} = 2 + s_6 + s_5 \left(1 + s_6 - s_7 - s_8 \right) + s_7 s_8.$$

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